

**GOVERNMENT REGULATION OF ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816261>

ABSTRACT In this article, state regulation of the economic security of the country, the introduction of innovations, ensuring the economic security of the country, its role and importance in its development, and the benefits of financing innovative projects are mentioned.

Key words: Innovation, economic security of the country, innovative ideas, innovative activity, know-how, "smart" technologies, economic competitiveness, marketing innovations, innovation potential, innovation sector, innovation program, innovation infrastructure

Two mechanisms of economic regulation have emerged in developed and transitioning to a market economy: state and market mechanisms. The purpose of science is to illuminate the specific features of state and market mechanisms. They are mixed and interconnected in life. It is desirable for them to be in an optimal relationship. The task of the science is to show the sectors and forms that have adopted the state mechanism together with market relations in the management of the economy, to analyze various concepts about the role of the state in the management of the economy. The market is one of the great achievements of human development. Its development has come a long way: this process starts from simple forms of communication between small producers and consumers to all forms of modern production activity, developed economic relations between economic subjects of society, covers the period from the creation of a social product to its consumption. The market is a complex mechanism coordinating various production and service activities. In this case, the social division of labor and private ownership are considered to be the decisive conditions of the market. In the market economy, the freedom of business activity and the material interests of producers are the main forces that encourage competition. It is known that an important element of the market is the price and its level, which is an important indicator for the producer, for the entrepreneur, and for the buyer. The market system is characterized by high flexibility and flexibility in the decision-making of producers and buyers. The market connects the producer and the consumer. The market mechanism is convenient for the effective distribution of resources between networks, ensuring the balance of supply and demand. In the development of the society's

economy, in the division of social labor, in the expansion of interstate relations, in economic processes such as the regulation of relations between the components of the economy, the regulatory possibilities of the market mechanism are shown to be limited. An example of this is the contradictions that arose in the economy during the economic crisis. The world economic crisis that occurred in 1929-1933 is a clear example. There are tasks of the process of social reproduction that the market mechanism cannot fulfill and regulate. In the development of industry, on the basis of free competition, production forces are growing not only within the framework of individual private property, but also the role of collective (shareholding) and other forms of ownership is increasing.

However, the state is forced to take over large sectors of the economy, to develop and regulate them. For example: railway, telegraph, post, defense, etc. There are also social functions that the market mechanism cannot fulfill. In addition, there is a need for state intervention in the results of some activities based on market relations.

This is, first of all, in regulating the economy at the macro level, providing social protection and assistance to a certain part of the population (unemployed, congenitally disabled), providing pensions, providing defense, solving environmental problems, social there is a need for state intervention in maintaining order, regulating money circulation, influencing the cycle of economic reproduction, and developing fundamental science. Foreign economic relations cannot be regulated without state intervention. The market mechanism cannot protect the interests of society, eliminate long-term social problems and problems arising in the mutual relations of countries. The state performs a number of economic tasks that the market mechanism cannot perform. They are as follows: 1. Ensuring social and economic security of the country and competitiveness of the national economy; 2. Stabilization tasks (regulating money circulation, preventing inflation, etc.); 3. The task of legal regulation; 4. Coordination task; 5. Socially oriented task; 6. Distribution; 7. Control and others. All of the above shows that the regulation of the economy through the market mechanism is as necessary as the state mechanism is necessary in the modern economy. The most important thing is to combine the advantages of both mechanisms in the regulation of economic processes. This is one of the important tasks in the rational management of the economy.

During the period of self-regulation of the economy, the market mechanism became the only mechanism for regulating the economy for a long time. The

need to develop the economy by the state and harmonize it with the market arose a little later. The development of state regulation of the economy can be divided into two major stages: 1. Before the Second World War; 2. After the Second World War. At the first stage, the state created favorable conditions for the reproduction of private capital: labor, tax, trade and social legislation frameworks were developed. During the period of free competition, the state began to participate in the economic process by expanding private capital in the construction of military factories and railways. At the same time, the state begins to regulate certain sectors (agrarian sector, money and credit...). In the second stage, a number of countries increased the activity of planning sectors, programming national and regional development, regulating the economy in the state budget and credit sector. State intervention in economic development has a general economic character, and the state has developed long-term strategic goals. This stage describes the activities of the state according to the medium-term state agreements of the international level within the framework of the integration unions. Types of state regulation: absolute state monopoly (former union and other countries) and levels of economic freedom, that is, there are a number of intermediate forms between these levels (market socialism in China, social way in Germany and Austria oriented market economy, Swedish mixed economy model, etc.). The mentioned methods of regulation by the state are divided into straight and crooked methods. The right methods include: state subsidies, state entrepreneurship, and the system of state management of the economy. Indirect methods include: taxes, fines, quotas, customs duties, etc. Indicative planning and state programs are an important form of state regulation of the economy.

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